

ARTIP STATUS REPORT

M. B. Leahy Jr

AFMC Robotics and Automation Center of Excellence
Technology and Industrial Support Directorate
Specialized Engineering Branch, Advanced Process Technology Section
San Antonio Air Logistics Center, Kelly AFB, TX 78241
ti-race@sadis05.kelly.af.mil

Abstract

The Air Force Material Command Advanced Robotics Technology Insertion Program (ARTIP) was formally initiated in August 1992. The ARTIP Program Action Directive (PAD) codifies the mission and responsibilities that the AFMC Robotics and Automation Center of Excellence (RACE) has been actively pursuing since October 1991. AFMC RACE is a command wide focal point, an organic source of expertise to assist the logistic and product centers in improving process productivity through the judicious insertion of robotics and automation technologies. This paper provides an overview of the ARTIP PAD and an update on major RACE activities in support of those objectives.

1 Introduction

In August 1992, the Robotics and Automation Center of Excellence (RACE) received the Advanced Robotics Technology Insertion Program (ARTIP) Program Action Directive (PAD) from HQ AFMC/XPXM. Before receiving the PAD, RACE was operating with the authority of a letter from HQ AFLC/XP designating SA-ALC the lead ALC on advanced robotics and supporting automation technology [6, 7]. The PAD formalizes RACE's role as the program manager (PM) for advanced robotics and supporting hardware and software automation with the responsibility for applied technology research and implementation of robotics and supporting automation technologies.

The salient features of the ARTIP scope are outlined in section two. The remainder of this paper

discusses the status of the RACE efforts to execute those objectives. Top priority is immediate customer support. Section three describes how RACE team members support product directorate engineers, the project areas our efforts are concentrated on, and the initiatives undertaken to support future requirements. A major function of a real center of excellence is the creation and utilization of a prototype center. Section four describes the capabilities of that evolving customer support tool. Conclusions are in section five. A complete overview of RACE activities is beyond the scope of this document.

2 ARTIP PAD

AFMC RACE serves as the center for advanced (applied research) robotics and supporting automation technologies within the Command. Each center will actively participate and support the ARTIP PM in achieving the Command's advanced robotic objectives. The centers are already involved to some degree with applied robotics and supporting automation technologies. This involvement will dramatically increase to champion further development and promote new cost effective industrial processes as they relate to old and new weapon system applications.

The purpose of the ARTIP is to utilize emerging robotics and supporting automation technologies to address and solve reliability and maintainability (R&M) problems associated with supporting existing Air Force weapon systems and to develop industrial capabilities by judicious applications. Developing AFMC capability will aid greatly in the supportability of future weapon systems, which need the new

or emerging robotic technologies.

Solutions to R&M problems will be accomplished by applied technology insertion projects at all of the centers. Technology insertion projects will be developed and solutions simulated and prototyped, utilizing advanced robotic and supporting automation technologies. Capabilities throughout the Command will be enhanced by advanced robotics technology demonstrated through prototypes and simulations, mechanisms, distribution of training material, transition and cross-feed of technology reference data. RACE will lead this effort so as to minimize duplication and ensure that all centers benefit from advanced robotic technology.

3 Customer Support

The RACE team provides technical support throughout the life cycle of a robotics project. The level of support depends on the technical background of the product directorate engineer [6]. During our first year of operation, we grouped individual insertion projects into five major categories [7]. We have further refined those categories into four main project support areas and two technical initiatives.

3.1 Project Support Areas

Project areas span multiple applications across all the depots. For more detailed information on any of these projects or sponsors, please contact the RACE office directly.

3.1.1 Corrosion Control

RACE activities in corrosion control encompass multiple efforts to apply advanced robotic and automation technology to all aspects of the paint removal and application process. The range of applications stretches from piece parts to the C-5 fuselage. Process engineers responsible for corrosion control are being drawn to robotic systems due to efforts to eradicate the chemical stripping processes. Alternative paint removal techniques, while not environmentally hazardous, can be unsuitable for human application. High pressure (18K psi) water jet, CO₂ ice pellets, flash lamps and lasers based application tools must be mounted as robot end-effectors. Even ignoring the obvious physical dangers, the application

tools are too heavy (50 lbs or greater) for continuous human operation. Plastic Media Bead (PMB) and sodium bicarbonate blasting can be performed by operators in special air breathing suits, but the task is monotonous and messy. Another automation driver is the desire for stringent processes control. Many of the alternative stripping methods remove paint by blasting the aircraft or part with some media. Blasting introduces stress into the substrate leading to reduced fatigue life. Tight control of the blasting process is necessary to minimize those side effects. Robotic systems provide a level of process control superior to that of a human operator. The unfriendly application environment, heavy payload, repetitive non-contact nature of the task, and requirement for tight process control, make the paint stripping operation ideally suited for robotic intervention.

After stripping the plane and repairing any damage, it must be repainted. Environmental, quality, and cost considerations are driving the depots to the same solution adopted by the automotive industry. Unfortunately, the solution does not scale directly from an Escort to a C-5. On the positive side, the basic capabilities of a stripping system carry over to the paint application. Commercial robot manipulators can perform the stripping and painting task. The remaining technical issues are: how to transport them around large aircraft, the level of autonomy required, and how to reduce the insertion costs.

There are three major approaches to the aircraft transport problem. The SAFARI system, operational at WR-ALC, uses a rail guided positioner to move a commercial spray painting robot around an F-15 [2]. Along with changing the floor location and height, the SAFARI positioner also has a linear sliding axis to position the paint robot over and under the aircraft. A different positioner concept is under development as part of the Large Aircraft Robotic Paint Stripper (LARPS) REPTECH project at OC-ALC [5]. The LARPS positioner is a large SCARA arm riding up and down on a column attached to an automated guide vehicle (AGV). The end-effector is a new commercial robot. The major differences between the LARPS and SAFARI approaches are in guidance and application. LARPS is wire guided with a SCARA coarse positioner. SAFARI rides on rails and relays on a linear seventh axis. Formal

tradeoff studies await the successful implementation of the LARPS prototype.

The third approach follows a completely different thought process. Both SAFARI and LARPS are big (50K lbs), expensive (\$1.5-2M), fully automated systems. A primary objective was to minimize the labor rates associated with the painting or stripping process. But the masking and general preparation are not easily automated, and they form a major portion of the overall painting/stripping process. At least half of the total process remains very manpower intensive. That observation motivated the AF corrosion control office at WR-ALC to sponsor development of a prototype automated stripping tool that helps the operators instead of eliminating them. Tool development is a component of a broad design philosophy which seeks to solve the large positioner problem by attaching a commercial robot or customer mechanism to an existing manual lift platform. The operator acts in a supervisory role, moving the platform into place, calibrating the stripping rate, inspecting the stripped area and then repeating the cycle. The actual stripping process is performed by a robotic device which calibrates itself to the surface area and then proceeds to perform the stripping/painting task within its workspace. Upon completion, the robot calls the supervisor to inspect and touch-up as required. The robotic system is not responsible for all paint removal, hard to reach areas are still accomplished by the human operators necessary for the aircraft preparation. This approach has a particular appeal for existing corrosion control hangers at SA-ALC and WR-ALC which are equipped with electric telecranes. These telecrane platforms allow human operators to access large portions of the aircraft surface. The cranes lack the sophisticated control and position measurement devices necessary for judicious conversion to fully automated control. But they are paid for, can carry the weight of an automated end-effector system and eliminate direct human involvement from over 80% of the stripping process. The supervisory control aspects of the Cargo Arms concept are one of the major drivers behind our telerobotics initiative.

Regardless of what systems are eventually chosen for both the airframe and backshop applications, the key to lower insertion costs will be standardization.

We can not afford to develop entirely new systems for each airframe and ALC. We need to determine what works and what doesn't and then replicate the success stories throughout the depots. The RACE is working closely with the owners of the current development efforts, and prospective customers at the other ALCs, to insure that judicious solutions to this important problem are implemented.

3.1.2 Industrial Automation

This category encompasses a diverse variety of projects where our mission is strictly technology pull. The necessary equipment is commercially available and the basic process has been successfully applied in industry. Our role is to make the directorate engineers aware of the technology and assist in the implementation. Small projects in this class will be completed with organic engineering skills. A detailed discussion of a current organic engineering effort highlights the type of projects conducted in this area.

The RACE has teamed up with the Non-destructive Inspection/Testing Branch (TIELN) at SA-ALC to create the concept of an Automated X-Ray Evaluation System (AXES). Our customer is responsible for inspecting components of the F100, TF39, and T56 engines, castings for the T-38 trainer aircraft, B-52 airframe components, and various Conformance Verification Program items. The emergence of the C-17 cargo aircraft is expected to further increase their workload. The X-ray inspections are currently accomplished by positioning an x-ray tube at certain positions and orientations in space using a manually operated chain hoist. The tube is a cylinder with an 18" diameter and a weight of 165 pounds and must be uniquely positioned for each of several different exposures for each of the many components to be inspected. The critical target-independent parameters for each exposure are focal length, power setting, length of exposure (time), and angle of attack. The current positioning method is time consuming and inaccurate. Operators are required to manually move the tube to approximately the correct position, measure the distance to the subject, and adjust until the distance is reasonably close to the desired value. The operator's view of the part to be inspected is obscured by the X-ray tube itself, therefore he/she

has no instantaneous feedback while making these adjustments, and must move, stop, measure, and repeat until acceptable results are obtained. This process is complicated by the fact that many exposures require a fine adjustment of the exposure angle; in order to inspect a seam, for instance. The distance and angle adjustments are not independent of one another, making the total fine-tuning of the tube position a very arduous task.

TIELN asked the RACE to help put together a PRAM (Productivity, Reliability, Availability, and Maintainability) project to improve this process. The solution we are implementing is to replace the hoist and chain assembly with a commercially available six degree-of-freedom industrial robot and couple it with a new state-of-the-art X-ray tube. A one degree-of-freedom turntable will be used to position parts within the robot work envelope. The advantage of the robot is that a large majority of the workload of the inspection group is concentrated on about 15 components. The robot will be programmed to memorize the correct positions for these components and will place the X-ray tube exactly where needed for the exposures in a small fraction of the time now needed. Also, on the remaining unique items to be inspected, the operator will be able to move the X-ray tube with the hand-held teach pendant while observing the relative placement of the tube. Even this non-automated approach will be several times faster than the current method. The new X-ray tube will be connected to the robot's controller which will make all the necessary exposure settings (X-ray strength, exposure duration, etc.) automatically. The system is expected to save the Air Force over \$2 million (net) over ten years while improving the quality of life of our customers. The AXES robotic subsystem is being designed for applicability to a variety of other backshop process applications.

3.1.3 Retrofits

Several installed robotic systems have serious reliability and maintainability problems. We are assisting the product directorates in determining the most prudent course of action in eliminating those problems. Our services range from determining the technical nature of the problem, to proposing a solution,

and then assisting in solution implementation. The primary emphasis at the moment involves replacement of the Modicon 5200 controllers installed in five paint stripping robots [3], and one automatic derivetor system [1]. The Modicon is no longer in production. Spare parts are very rare and system software is not easily transportable. These designs were cursed with no evolutionary path for hardware or software upgrades. A complete controller retrofit is required if these systems are to remain in production. WR-ALC has an active project to upgrade the controller and mechanical systems of their three stripping robots. Lessons learned from that project will be applied to the other three systems.

The magnitude of the robot retrofit problem pales in comparison to the potential for machine tool retrofit applications. Each ALC has hundreds of machine tools which could benefit from marked advances in controller technology. The precision, productivity, and flexibility of the existing machines could be enhanced with retrofits at a fraction of the cost of replacement. RACE is attempting to use an ALC as a beta test site for the Next Generation Controller (NGC) program. NGC is a MANTECH initiative to revitalize the domestic machine tool industry by developing a standard around which advanced controller could be developed. A mature NGC standard would greatly reduce the insertion cost of advanced controller technology.

3.1.4 Airframe Repair

Repair of airframes is a significant workload at the logistic centers. Development of robotic systems for airframe repair has concentrated on rivet removal. The Navy initiated a mobile derivetor project in 1983 [4]. The project objectives were too ambitious for the existing technology base and the end product was a large, complex system with limited flexibility that was not well received by shop personnel. The REPTECH office funded the development of a Robotic Deriveting and Drilling Cell installed at OO-ALC [1]. This system was designed to remove all of the rivets from a rigidly fixtured, F-4 inboard flap. The tooling is being purchased to allow that system to be used on a current workload. WR-ALC is supporting a multi-phase contract to develop a gantry

based vision guided system for reskinning F-15 wings. The Automated Aircraft Rework System (AARS) is being designed to remove all of the fasteners found on an F-15 wing and then to replicate the hole pattern so that a new skin can be attached without prestressing the frame [10]. That system is in prototype design after a successful concept demonstration on a real wing. The AARS is generic enough to be utilized for a wide range of airframe repair tasks. If the full scale prototype meets expectations, we will look to insert this technology across the command.

Other future applications, like flexible laser/water jet cutting and surface finishing systems, are pushing the telerobotic initiative.

3.2 Technology Initiatives

The RACE is chartered to seek out and champion technologies whose increased development and eventual application will have a positive impact across a broad range of depot processes. Our main interest is to expand the application range and reduce the insertion cost of robotic systems. The overall objective is to foster the development of robotic systems that fit the PC analogy; an inexpensive, flexible platform which has a large support and software base and is easily customized for a particular application. To accomplish that vision, the ideas of reconfigurable software, modular robots, and standardized interfaces must be fully developed. Those concepts are embedded in our two major technology initiatives.

3.2.1 Telerobotics

Telerobotic technologies will play an increasing part in the solutions to ALC productivity enhancement problems. Unfortunately, telerobotics is not an off-the-shelf technology. The basic components exist, and prototypes exist in various forms in university and government laboratories. However, the vital step of system integration for shop floor utilization has not been completed. We are faced with a unique opportunity and challenge. Properly developed, telerobotic systems will have a large impact on both depot and commercial applications. The challenge is to avoid the mistakes of the past, avoid developing *one-of* systems and concentrate early efforts on creation of a generic system that supports a large range

of applications and provides an evolutionary path for incorporating new technologies and reducing life cycle costs. Additional information on this initiative is contained in a companion paper [8].

3.2.2 Mobile Robots for NDI

As the age of our cargo aircraft increases, so does the requirement for Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) of large wing and fuselage areas. The human operator is well suited for making judgements about the meaning of sensor readings. Unfortunately, the operator is not well suited to the highly repetitious and often awkward manipulation of the sensor suite. A robotic assistant is needed to assume the sensor manipulation task, thereby dramatically enhancing overall inspection accuracy and efficiency. The large robot systems in section 3.1.1 are well suited to painting/stripping applications where the process is traditionally accomplished in large dedicated hangers. However, large systems are not appropriate for flightline NDI applications. The customer wants a small self contained manipulation system capable of putting the light weight sensors at any location on the aircraft surface. Our emphasis in this initiative is the definition of the mobile robot system best suited to those functions [7].

3.3 Internal Initiatives

Along with the direct project support and technical initiatives, the RACE is also pursuing several additional initiatives which will lead to improved customer support. In direct support of AFMC objectives, we are working with the national laboratories to transfer technology to the shop floor. We have working relationships with the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Sandia National Laboratory, and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) robotics programs. We are negotiating a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with the Armstrong Laboratory telerobotics group while pursuing better working relationships with AFOSR and DARPA. In concert with the belief that an educated customer is the best type of customer, RACE markets a 20 hour short course entitled Industrial Robotics: Today and Tomorrow. The most extensive internal project is the creation of a prototype center.

4 Prototype Center

To fully support the ARTIP objectives, RACE must have the tools to simulate/visualize and prototype solutions across the entire spectrum of potential logistic and product center applications. The planning and procurement of the hardware and software necessary to establish a state-of-the-art robotics and automation prototype center has been a top priority. The center, which should be fully operational in July, provides an enhanced level of customer support in the following areas:

4.1 Simulation/Visualization

The most important tools in the RACE prototype center are the simulation platforms. Two Silicon Graphics Indigo Elan graphical workstations and a SUN Sparc 2 are running the latest CAD and robot workcell simulation/off-line programming software. Supported software includes Cimstation, IGRIP, and Robline 3D color solid modeling robot simulation packages. That software environment provides the unique capability, within the Air Force, to carry solution development from initial concept through actual robot code generation. The software has sophisticated functions such as collision detection, and graphical libraries for many of the commercially available industrial robots. RACE employs that capability to show its customers the functionality of a proposed solution, greatly reducing technical risk and increasing the likelihood of procuring a production suitable system. One can envision a future where a video tape of the simulated workcell is provided, as part of the RFP package, to succinctly convey the functionality expected of the proposed system. That software is being used to design the AXES and to evaluate alternative Cargo Arms designs. Reach and speed studies for the SAFARI and LARPS concepts are also planned, once their models are loaded.

4.2 Concept Validation

Simulation is a critical step in the design process, and the new environments substantially reduce the time line from concept to implementation, but they are not perfect. Simulation software is kinematically not dynamically based and typically does not give a precise representation of the actual control algorithms

found in a real system. Another serious limitation is the inability to incorporate sensory feedback into the simulation. There is still no substitute for test and evaluation on representative physical hardware. The prototype center will contain a representative set of robotic systems to evaluate and demonstrate the proposed solutions and emerging technologies. Physical simulation is another key step in reducing insertion risk.

Three state-of-the-art industrial robots will complement an American Robot MERLIN and Unimation PUMA. While the MERLIN never was state-of-the-art, its large reach and payload are valuable physical simulation tools and fill a niche. The new robots are:

- Adept One with Hyperdrive, fully integrated vision, and force sensor systems
- Fanuc Robotics S-10 RJ with fully integrated vision system
- Adept 604-S

Along with directly serving customer needs, the industrial robots are a linchpin in our efforts to build and maintain organic expertise. To acquire a true appreciation for any technology, engineers must have the opportunity to put their ideas to the test. The Adept One and S-10 represent two of the most sophisticated robotic systems on the market and when combined with full vision systems are capable of prototyping any solutions that are commercially viable. Our facilities are also employed in the education and training of ALC personnel. The little 604-S was brought to serve as an educational and off-site demonstration device. With the 604-S, one gets the full sophistication of the Adept control system in a portable package. All of the robots can be off-line programmed by our existing simulation systems. We hope to have the new robots installed and operational by the end of July.

4.3 Technology Demonstrators

Emerging technologies can not always be properly evaluated on existing industrial systems. To account for those instances and support our applied research function, we have implemented an advanced robotics

technology demonstration platform. The platform consists of a PUMA 560 manipulator controlled by a research based robot operating system running on a multiprocessor VME based computer system. Currently, we are running the CHIMERA robotic operating system developed at Carnegie Mellon University [9], but the system is generic enough to support a multitude of different configurations. With a PUMA as the manipulator, the system is limited to demonstration of new software algorithms. But since the PUMA is the dominant university robot, and 80% of robotics is software, we don't view that as a limitation.

Technology demonstration is not restricted to a single building. We have acquired two surplus T3-7XX class manipulators. The T3's will be retrofitted with advanced control systems in order to evaluate various telerobotic concepts in a shop floor environment. One of the test applications will be surface finishing of C-5 engine cowlings. Insight into actual operator preferences is a vital component in our telerobotics initiative.

5 Conclusions

The Air Force Material Command Robotics and Automation Center of Excellence (RACE) is implementing the objectives of the Advanced Robotics Technology Insertion Program (ARTIP) Program Action Directive. The RACE provides a command-wide focal point for process engineers who seek to improve efficiency through the judicious insertion of robotics and automation technology. RACE is a champion for pulling emerging technologies into the Aircraft Logistics Centers. The RACE team is currently providing technical support to process engineers at all five ALCs. Major project support areas are corrosion control, industrial automation, retrofits, and airframe repair. Technology initiatives in the areas of telerobotics and mobile robots for NDI are underway. A comprehensive prototype center stands ready to provide state-of-the-art support to our customers. The RACE team is ready to work with you. Join us as we champion competitive processes through intelligent machines.

References

- [1] G. S. Bettencourt, Robotic Deriveting and Drilling Cell, *Proc of REPTECH 89*, Oklahoma City, OK, Aug 22-24, 1989.
- [2] H. Berry, Robotic Aircraft Painting with SAFARI, *Proc of the SME Conf on Maintaining and Supporting an Aircraft Fleet*, Dallas, TX, Jun 9-11, 1992.
- [3] E. A. Franke, Automated Paint Stripping, *Proc of REPTECH 89*, Oklahoma City, OK, Aug 22-24, 1989.
- [4] E. A. Franke, Update on the Robotic Derivator, *Proc of Fastec West '86*, Anaheim, CA, Oct 21-23, 1986.
- [5] S. Hofacker, Large Aircraft Robotic Paint Stripping, *Proc of the SME Conf on Maintaining and Supporting an Aircraft Fleet*, Dallas, TX, Jun 9-11, 1992.
- [6] M. B. Leahy, Jr. and B. K. Cassiday, Towards RACE, *Proc of the SME Conf on Maintaining and Supporting an Aircraft Fleet*, Dallas, TX, Jun 9-11, 1992.
- [7] M. B. Leahy, Jr. and B. K. Cassiday, RACE Pulls for Shared Control, *Proc of SPIE Conf on Cooperative Intelligent Robotics in Space III*, Boston, MA, Nov 16-18, 1992.
- [8] M. B. Leahy, Jr. and S. B. Petroski, Telerobotics for Depot Applications, *Proc of NAECON 93*, Dayton, OH., May 1993.
- [9] D. B. Stewart, D. E. Schmitz, and P. K. Khosla, Implementing Real-Time Robotic Systems Using CHIMERA II, *Proc of the IEEE Int Conf on Systems Eng*, Pittsburgh, PA, Aug 9-11, 1990.
- [10] *Automated Aircraft Rework System System Specification*, Mercer Engineering Research Center, Warner Robbins, GA.